

"Listen, Sing, Speak and Succeed: Developing Speaking Skills Through Musical Activities"

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Annotation The article offers the potential of using music to improve learners' speaking skills in language learning and explores the strategies, and applications of incorporating music-based activities in enhancing learners' speaking proficiency.

Keywords: *Music-based speaking activities, productive and receptive skills, integration of four skills, pre-, while and post-stages of the lesson, strengths and weaknesses in language learning*

Annotatsiya Maqolada o'quvchilarning til o'rganishda nutq ko'nikmalarini yaxshilash uchun musiqadan foydalanish imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi va o'quvchilarning nutq mahoratini oshirishda musiqaga asoslangan faoliyatni birlashtirish strategiyalari va qo'llanilishi bo'yicha kerakli tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Musiqaga asoslangan nutq faoliyati, produktiv va retseptiv mahorat, to'rtta ko'nikmaning integratsiyasi, darsning boshlang'ich, o'rta va so'nggi bosqichlari, til o'rganishdagi kuchli va zaif tomonlar.*

Аннотация В статье обсуждаются возможности использования музыки для улучшения разговорных навыков учащихся при изучении языка, а также приводятся полезные рекомендации по стратегиям и применениям интеграции деятельности, основанной на музыке, для улучшения разговорных навыков учащихся.

Ключевые слова: *Разговорная деятельность под музыку, продуктивные и рецептивные навыки, интеграция четырех навыков, этапы до, во время и после урока, сильные и слабые стороны в изучении языка.*

In the modern world, planning a lesson with only modern pedagogical technologies and creating a learner-centered environment in the educational process is one of the main issues facing today's pedagogues.

In language teaching, it is impossible to surprise students by teaching grammatical rules with a limited number of new words given for 1 lesson, repeating them, organizing the lesson based on the grammar translation method from the beginning till the ending. This approach, furthermore, does not correspond to the current teaching methodology at all, and can not be accepted as one of the productive ways to develop students' language learning skills. [8; p.11]

It is important to develop sub-skills such as grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation in language teaching, but it is also important to develop the integration of

four skills in the practical application of the acquired knowledge. Many people believe that in language teaching, it is better to develop grammar, vocabulary first and then to develop productive and receptive skills. Is it really so? Do sub skills and skills need to be developed separately, or do students make more progress if they focus more on developing both together? This article, regardless of learners’ age difference, interest, and level of competence, offers suggestions on how to effectively use music as one of the main tools in teaching integrated language skills. In addition, by using several activities and tasks based on music, the possibilities of improvements in receptive and productive skills are analyzed by developing subskills such as grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary of language learners. [7; p. 330]

In language teaching, if we want to teach using modern innovative teaching methods, we use tasks and activities based on various tools. [6; p.1084] Among them, it is permissible to highlight music. Music is a tool that can be used to increase the level of different learners in the teaching process, and most importantly, it is a widely used tool at the goal and stage of any lesson.

Within the topics, we often use music in the introduction (pre) and closing (post stages) of the lesson to improve listening skills, to memorize words or to perform tasks aimed at checking the level of memory. In fact, have you ever thought about the other types of music-based linking activities we have and what they can be used for? [10; p.468]

In addition to listening to music and discussing what it is about during the lesson, the following tasks can be developed and used in the lesson. Let’s talk about the different music-related activities that I have used a lot in my experience, strategies for using them, and their benefits. I believe that these assignments will help students to improve their productive and receptive skills, as well as sub-skills such as grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary, when designing lesson plans and creating different activities using music.

Activities....

- **Find the title and theme of the music.** In this task, the title of the music is not given in the lyrics, but the learners predict the name of the music after listening it and tell what it is about based on the words they understand. In this case, music is selected depending on the ease or difficulty of the words in the lyrics, or the learners’ level. It is mainly used at the beginning of the lesson.

- **Find the type of music and explain why it is ...** (pop music, jazz, hip hop or folk). This task is used to focus students’ attention in the pre-stage of the lesson or to strengthen a whole topic in the post-stage if the lesson is about music, and also helps to improve learners’ logical thinking and speaking skills.

- **Questions based on the information given in the song.** After listening to the song, a series of questions are asked to check learners’ understanding and impressions. Based on the answers to the questions, the learners practice the words they have memorized and gain additional information by listening to each other. This will definitely

develop their speaking and listening comprehension skills. The song is chosen according to the learners' level of competence and can be used at all stages of the lesson. [11; p. 83]

- **Fill in the gaps.** This task can be done in two main ways. 1st way: young learners are given the lyrics of a song sung in their native language (for example, Uzbek or Russian) (some words are omitted in the lines) and while listening to the song, they find the necessary words and are ordered to write them in their target language (code mixing). It allows them to do multitasking at the same time. In the second way, learners are given lyrics with missing words and are asked to listen and find the omitted words while listening to the music. [11, p.80]

In both methods, learners can develop listening, speaking skills and learn translation of unknown words in the song. When finding omitted words, they can logically think of what part of speech can be based on the grammatical structure of the words that come before and after the omitted words.

- **Write a song and sing it.** Half of the song text (lyrics) are given to learners and listened to until that half. The rest are asked to compose and sing based on their creativity. In this case, the learners will have to create a text related to the content without changing the theme of the beginning of the song text. Learners not only improve speaking and listening competencies, but also develop creative writing skills. They feel themselves as composers and singers and apply their knowledge of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar in practice. This activity can be used for all types of learners, mainly post stage of the lesson.

- **Prediction.** Music is played and learners listen. They are then asked if there is any connection between the song and the new topic. Based on the theme of the song, they guess the new topic to be discussed in today's lesson. Learners give their guesses and explain why they made such guesses. All guesses will be listened to and a new theme will be announced by the teacher. At the pre stage of the lesson, this activity is carried out to interest learners in a new topic, and the teacher must choose a song related to the topic. This activity can be used for learners of all levels. [4; p.50]

- **Laugh, cry, but sing anyway.** The lyrics are given to the students and the song is played. Students are divided into 4 groups and each group is given a couplet of the song. The first group sings a couplet in a monotone voice without using any high or low pitches. The second group laughs and sings the given couplet. They should not stop laughing while singing. The third group also sings, but they have to sing as if they are crying or sad. The fourth group sings using body language. Thus, the song is sung by learners in different situations. Pronunciation problems are eliminated.

- **True/False statement.** True/False statements are read based on information from the song and learners select each statement as True or False based on the information provided in the lyrics. It is used in all stages of the lesson, mainly in the while stage, and useful for improving the listening, speaking and logical thinking skills of learners of all levels. They explain why it is false or true using their vocabulary.

- **Extra words.** Extra words are written on each line of the lyrics and given to the learners. In the process of listening to a song, learners find redundant, unspoken words in the lyrics lines. In the pre and post stage can be used, it is mainly productive for beginners and pre-intermediate level learners.[9; p. 9]

- **Misorder- order.** Lines or couplets in the song are arranged or ordered incorrectly. As they listen to the song, they determine the order of each line or couplet. After they are identified, everyone sings the song together.

- **Finding the number of parts of speech in the song.** This is mainly used in grammar-based lessons. The song is listened to and learners are asked to find how many of the phrases are used in the lyrics. For example, 10 verbs are involved, 5 are regular verbs and 5 are analyzed as irregular verbs.

Through listening and speaking, their knowledge of grammar is strengthened, and everyone corrects mistakes in the analysis together. It can be used at all stages of the lesson, it is mainly used in the post stage for the purpose of checking the grammar rules of a certain part of speech.

- **Identifying the grammatically incorrect form of words (adjective, adverbs, nouns).** In the lyrics, the grammatical forms of some words (for example "fishes", "beutifuller") are given incorrectly. While listening to the song, they identify the wrong forms of the words and find the correct ones through discussion. This activity will be more useful if it is mainly used for teaching grammar. It is a fruitful activity that develops all skills and subskills at the same time.[1; p.6]

- **Find spelling mistakes.** Learners are given some words in the lyrics with spelling mistakes. They will have to listen to the song and find spelling mistakes to correct. They will have to listen to the song and find spelling mistakes. This task, in turn, helps to overcome any grammar or writing deficiencies of the learners.

- **Synonyms and antonyms.** Learners choose at least 10 words from the song and say the synonyms and antonyms they have memorized for each of them. With the help of conjunctions, they make sentences using these synonyms and antonyms. They will have opportunities to use the words they have learned through grammar. It can be said that this is the most important activity for developing productive skills as well.

- **The definition to the words in lyrics.** Words included in the lyrics are selected and students give definition to these words using their own vocabulary. This activity can be used in all stages of the lesson.[10; p 467]

- **Matching.** Each couplet is numbered. Their main content is defined by letters. After learners listen to the song, couplets and their themes are matched. It is mainly used on the pre or post stages of the lesson.[5; p.100]

- **Music+drawing.** Learners are divided into 3 or 4 groups. a special song is played to each group, (it should not be played to other groups) they draw a picture based on the information in the music while listening to it. Each group guesses which song and what its theme is based on the pictures drawn by the other groups. This is especially useful if

it is used in the pre stage or post stage, where all skills and subskills are developed at the same time.

- **Music + role play or story.** After listening to the music, they role play or create a story based on the information given in it. Depending on their creativity, they create several characters and dialogues between them and act like actors. Or they use fantasy and make music-based stories and read them to everyone. Through this task, learners identify their own strengths and weaknesses in language learning and try to eliminate the shortcomings. It can be easily applied to learners of all levels.

- **Summary.** Learners listen to the music and write a summary based on the information given in it. In summary, they can also give themselves advice and motivation based on their impressions. It can be done at the post stage of the lesson to test how well learners understand the song and how much they are able to speak the theme of the song in their own words.[3; p.315]

- **Composer and Information provider.** In this task, students are divided into 2 groups and 2 different lyrics are pasted on the board. Each group will have one writer and the rest of the learners will be information providers. In the given period, the informants go to the blackboard in turn, read the text of the song and deliver it to the composer. Composer creates the lyrics based on the information given by each information provider. Then a whole group sings this song together. When providing information, the original song lyrics may change due to various reasons (excitement, memory loss, or an unknown word). This activity is mostly applied at the final stage of the lesson, with learners who have a level higher than the pre-intermediate. It will be beneficial for learners who have deficiencies related to listening, speaking, vocabulary, and pronunciation.

- **Cover up.** Learners are given the lyrics and listen to the song. Learners compose and sing music based on the given lyrics in groups during the allotted time. Then the original song and their cover songs are compared and the other band members give their feedback. Such tasks should be done to solve problems related to phonology.

- **D-W-D.** This activity is called definition - word-definition. A song is played and the lyrics are reviewed. We prepare as many cards as there are students in the group. Each card contains one word and one definition. The words are taken from the lyrics. In card 1, the definition is given first, then the word. On the other cards, the word is given first, then the definition. The student who receives Card 1 reads the definition first. On another card, a word corresponding to this definition is given. Everyone listens attentively and on which card this word is given, the owner of this card raises his hand and informs which word it is. The learner then reads the definition on the card and whoever has the required word on the card raises his hand and says the word. In this way, the words and definitions on all the cards are reviewed. This task can attract all learners and is a very useful activity for listening and vocabulary enhancement. It can be used at all stages of the lesson and for all types of level learners.

- **MCQ- multiple choice questions.** After listening to the song, it is possible to check how much the learners understand the lyrics of the song through special multiple

choice questions. Through such activities, along with listening comprehension, speaking competence, and logical thinking of learners can be developed. This activity can be done in all parts of the lesson and for all level learners. [2; p.502]

- **Word formation**- Making different parts of speech (develop- development-developed-developing- undeveloped) or creating different forms from the same word (good-better-the best) based on the given words in the song. This task is aimed at developing grammar knowledge through listening and can be done at all three stages of the lesson for learners of all levels.

-**Translation**. When it comes to translating a song, we often use two methods. In the 1st method, the song is listened to and the words are given to the students couplet by couplet. Pupils translate the given songs into their mother tongue. The meaning should be preserved in the translation, but the forms can be modified according to the students' ability. This task is a process that shows the importance of the rhyme in the song and the extent to which the author can use his figurative language in the translation.

In the 2nd way, learners are invited to the board turn by turn. the teacher plays music for each student (the song is sung in the mother tongue or target languages). Learners explain the content of the song in the target language and sing the translation. The rest of the students will have to find out which song and who the singer is. When choosing a song, it will be easier to explain to everyone if it is chosen from well-known and popular songs. [10; p. 464]

- **Transcription**. After listening to the song, transcriptions of a series of words selected from the lyrics are displayed on the screen or given on paper. Learners read the transcription and find out words given in the lyrics. This task is used in lessons dedicated to teaching how to pronounce correctly for elementary level learners.

Conclusion

Through a range of interactive methods and demonstrations, learners will discover practical ways to incorporate music into speaking practice in online and offline learning. Strategies share opportunities with teachers to create and design activities that target the development of spoken language, critical and logical thinking from lyrics. As a result, participants will have the opportunity to experience firsthand how music can stimulate language production, increase motivation, and create a supportive and creative learning environment.

It is desirable to be aware of the cognitive and socio-cultural advantages of using music in language teaching and learning, and to use music as one of the main tools in the development of lessons in the educational process. Through this, it becomes easier to increase the quality of education, and to make learners interested in the language learning process, and it helps both the teacher and the language learners to enjoy the interactive methods of teaching. Students learn how music can improve memory and improve communication skills. Classes also consider the role of cultural awareness and sensitivity in selecting music that reflects students' interests and backgrounds. In addition, this article

discussed practical considerations for implementing music-based speaking activities in different language teaching contexts.

Overall, this paper encourages teachers, researchers and language professionals to use music to develop meaningful language learning experiences designed to improve and inspire learners’ productive and receptive skills, mainly speaking and listening skills.

References:

1. Abdukhayotovna A. K. The role of authentic materials to develop pupils’communicative competence in English classes at academic lyceums //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
2. Balachandran Vadivel, Nawroz Ramadan Khalil, Debarati Roy, Mathuranjali M., Using Music for Developing Language Skills in the English Language Classroom, Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Vol.12 No.12 (2021), 501-507p
3. Bokiev, D., Bokiev, U., Aralas, D., Ismail, L., & Othman, M. (2018). Utilizing music and songs to promote student engagement in ESL classrooms. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, 8(12), 314–332
4. Cifuentes, C. (2006). Songs in the English class: A strategy to encourage tenth graders' oral production. Profile Issues in Teachers Professional Development, (7), 47-58.
5. Eerola, P. S., and Eerola, T. (2014). Extended music education enhances the quality of school life. Music Education Research. 16 (1), 88-104.
6. Khamzaev S.A, Gilyazetdinov E.Z, Sulstonova N.A, Samanova Sh.B, “The problems of developing an ESP course and the importance of ESP teacher training on the example of Uzbekistan, Journal of Critical Reviews, ISSN- 2394-5125 Vol 7, Issue 7, 2020., 1080-1085p
7. Şevik, M. (2012). Developing young learners’listening skills. Kastamonu Educational Journal, (1), 327–340.
8. Shin, J. K. (2006). Ten helpful ideas for teaching English to young learners. English Teaching Forum, 44(2), 2-13.
9. Sulstonova, N. (2021). MODERNIZATON OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. Journal of foreign languages and linguistics, 4(9).
10. Sulstonova N.A., Intercultural Competence in Teaching Foreign Languages, SSN: 2235-767X Volume 07, Issue 6, June 2019, 463-468p
11. Tuxtayeva N.A., Technique of professional training of future English language teachers through development of linguistic competences// British View ISSN 2041-3963 Volume 8 Issue 4 2023 Universal impact factor 8.528 SJIF 2022: 4.629 – P 78-85